

EFFECTIVENESS OF LEARNING RIDDLES IN PRIMARY GRADES

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INTRODUCTION

The people expressed their conclusions, philosophical reasoning, which they received from their life experience through proverbs. Uzbek folk proverbs are diverse and diverse in theme. The proverb is an expression from the words of wisdom, which perfectly expresses the life experiences, conclusions of the people in artistic terms. The opinions and content that should be expressed in the articles will be widely covered. In our opinion, not a single event occurred in the existence of each proverb, which caused the event to be observed by a representative of our extremely intelligent, selective ancestors. The proverb is derived from the Arabic word "qavlun", which means the concept of the word. Hence, the proverb can be taken in the meaning of the word wisdom. When you ask each teenage boy about the Family, School, Motherland he will have little or no knowledge. It is also encountered in such cases that some elementary school children cannot independently, fully explain their thoughts, in their speeches three different excesses. Therefore, in order to overcome such problems, it will be of benefit to teach folk proverbs in order to clarify their speech. A lot of examples of proverbs, which are the product of folk oral creativity in the textbooks of primary classes, are elucidated.

MAIN PART

In the textbooks of primary classes, we can meet many proverbs on such topics as labor, seasons, motherland friendship, good and evil, respect for parents, adults. Here, we can take a look to some proverbs:

Yoz mevasi – qish xazinasi. (Summer fruit is a winter treasure.)

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the views of the pupils of the primary classes on the richness of speech, activity of speech, awareness, resourcefulness, agility, search ability and interest in proverbs and puzzles, which are the products of the oral creativity of the folk, and is subject to discussion.

Toza havo – ming dardga davo. (Fresh air is a cure for a thousand troubles.) (1 class textbook “Native language and reading literacy”, p. 50).

With the help of the above proverbs, we give our readers an understanding of nature, encourage the younger generation to love nature, teach it not to hang, not to poison. Because from nature we emphasize our own breathing, that if we get dirty we get sick. Kattaga hurmatda bo‘l, kichikka izzatda. (Be in respect of the adult, be in honor of the little one.)

Yaxshi so‘z qand yedirar, yomon so‘z pand yedirar. (2 class textbook “Native language and reading literacy”, p. 77)

The presented proverbs aimed to teach children to be kind, sweet, to respect the big and small as one, not to offend someone by saying hard, bad, on the contrary, to motivate him to rejoice.

Vatan ostonadan boshlanadi. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 15)

Halol mehnat yerda qolmas. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 15)

Kuch – birlikda. (3 class textbook “Reading”, p. 140)

It turns out that these folk Proverbs also serve to transport thoughts. Through these proverbs, we need to give readers a broader understanding of Motherland, diligence, mutual understanding, unity, we need to teach them to love the motherland, to protect it, to be a duck, to grow up as a faithful and worthy child in the future, and also to take into account the young characteristics of the pupils and to ask for examples of folk proverbs

Do‘stsiz boshim – tuzsiz oshim.

Mehnatli non shakar, mehnatsiz non zahar.

(4 class textbook “Reading”, p. 80)

These proverbs are about friendship and labor. When commenting on these proverbs, the teacher should explain to the readers what true friendship is. We need to teach to respect a friend, to be next to him, without leaving him when he worries about his head. A man who loves Labor should always be respected, everyone respects him, the bread found behind the Labor should be nondestructive and sweet, on the contrary, the bread found without honest labor should make a person suffer a thousand.

Through proverbs on various topics, which are presented in the textbooks of the primary classes, the worldview of students is established, their activity, linguistic competences are formed, perfection, moral perfection help them to become owners of such qualities.

One of the most amazing and smallest genres of folk oral creativity samples are riddles. This genre teaches children to be more observant, to know life perfectly, to be cynical. But it is not right to consider riddles in folklore only in young children, since in riddles say and find competitions adults also participate with interest. The riddle is also a tradition to ask a few questions to determine what is hidden in the riddle contest. The side looking for the answer is from the narrator: "is there a soul or not?", "is it eaten?",

"does it grow, does the master live?", something like asking questions tried to find the name. The question that can be solved in the riddles is expressed in a figurative form, and its meaning is hidden. In the riddles, the thing is traversed by analogy, mutual comparison, comparison with something else or phenomenon. The riddles are sometimes prose, often in poetic form, painfully and emotionally compact, simple and melodic.

Every young child, of course, is interested in finding, eagerly tries to find it. Without knowing whether the answer is right or wrong, he immediately tries to tell the thought that came to his mind. Taking into account these aspects, a lot of puzzles are presented in the textbooks of the primary class. Examples of the riddle genre do not leave readers indifferent, motivating them to resourcefulness, dexterity, insight. Although we explain the puzzles by connecting them with life. Young people at the moment are very perceptive, they can immediately notice everything. First of all, it would be worthwhile if we focused on the issue of the ratio of the puzzles presented in the textbooks of the primary school and the age of the child. In the textbook "mother tongue and literacy of reading" (Part 1, Page 47) the following Uzbek folk puzzles are presented:

Qo'lsiz, oyoqsiz eshik ochar. (shamol)

Oppoqqina dasturxon

Yer yuzini qoplagan. (qor)

O'tda yonmaydi, Suvda botmaydi. (muz)

The given riddles cannot be found by all pupils either. Teachers, as well as students through the pictures given in the book, try to find the answer, strive. The above examples can be included in the group of puzzles on nature.

And in the textbook "Mother tongue and reading literacy" (Part 1 98-page) of the 2nd Class, there are several riddles as shown below:

Bir tuyam bor, guldiroq,

Hamma yeri yaltiroq. (traktor)

Cho'zilib yotar narvon, Undan o'tar uy – karvon. (temir yo'l, poyezd)

Baland temir uy yurar, Burni tog'larni surar. (ekskovator)

Students will be able to accurately distinguish the incoming puzzles from the incoming puzzles into a group of puzzles that will be named items related to vehicles. In addition, it is possible that students will be able to know to what extent these vehicles will be used, for what purposes we will be able to use them, even if we create and clarify a problematic situation. And the places they do not know are understood by the teacher.

CONCLUSION

In summary, both proverbs and riddles, in addition to the upbringing of students, worldview, intellectual development, speech activity, good assimilation of the textbook, insightful, persuasive, examples of various subjects, provide a great help in educating representatives of the younger generation in the spirit of life-long, professional skills acquisition. Therefore, in the course of each lesson, it is clear to the reader that the

passage of Proverbs and riddles along with the interpretation is a good effect. Then they will go into the depths of the proverb and the riddles, carefully looking for the content expressed in it. Folk proverbs and riddles have been serving to improve people's lives for many centuries. The more important they are in our distant past, the more important they are today, the more important they are even after independence. Folk proverbs and Riddles, which have a special place in the spiritual rise of the younger generation, become an important source for the development of oral and written speech of our little ones and live from centuries to centuries.

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